

Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment MOdels for Net-zero, sustainable Development

D7.4 – The DIAMOND Project CDE Plan – Update 2

WP7 – Communicate, Disseminate & Exploit

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EC Summary Requirements

1. Changes with respect to the DoA

No changes with respect to the work described in the DoA.

2. Dissemination and uptake

This deliverable serves primarily as a reference document among consortium partners to support the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities of the project. It can also be used by other similar projects to draw from our planning (ambition) and implementation (experiences) so that they can in turn develop a robust CDE strategy.

3. Short summary of results

This report is the second update to the DIAMOND project's strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities to relevant audiences, submitted one year prior to the project's conclusion.

As in the initial CDE plan described in deliverable D7.2 (and its update in D7.3), this report first defines the scope of CDE in the context of DIAMOND and sets the overall targets of the project, which aims to follow a tailored approach to develop inclusive messages and convey them to specific audiences through efficient communication means. The report also sets quantifiable indicators for specific activities that will be tracked throughout the duration of the project, such as publishing at least 10 articles and press releases throughout the project.

Next, the report iterates the identification of the project's target audiences, which include modellers, researchers, policymakers, and industries, as well as NGOs and civil society organisations. A multi-pronged selection of promotional channels/platforms is suggested, to more effectively target these varied populations. The promotional channels to reach project audiences include the project's website, social media (e.g., X, LinkedIn, and Instagram), the IAM PARIS platform, synergies with other relevant projects, open-access papers, and more. A visual identity and a logo for the project have been developed and has been used throughout the project, including in the design of the project website and promotional materials such as infographics, presentations, and videos.

The plan concludes by reporting progress towards the CDE indicators, as of September 2025, and outlines the forthcoming actions aimed at enhancing dissemination and stakeholder engagement.

4. Evidence of accomplishment

This report.

Preface

DIAMOND will update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It will further enhance modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies. This will be done via integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establish vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATIONS AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	EL	
BC3	ASOCIACION BC3 BASQUE CENTRE FOR CLIMATE CHANGE - KLIMA ALDAKETA IKERGAI	ES	
CESAR	KRATENA KURT	AT	
CICERO	CICERO SENTER FOR KLIMAFORSKNING	NO	
CYI	THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE	CY	
E4SMA	ENERGY ENGINEERING ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENT SYSTEMS MODELING AND ANALYSIS SRL	IT	
HOLISTIC	HOLISTIC IKE	EL	
COMILLAS	UNIVERSIDAD PONTIFICIA COMILLAS	ES	
ISINNOVA	ISTITUTO DI STUDI PER L'INTEGRAZIONE DEI SISTEMI (I.S.I.S) - SOCIETA' COOPERATIVA	IT	
SEURECO	SEURECO SOCIETE EUROPEENNE D'ECONOMIE SARL	FR	
UM	UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT	NL	
ESMIA	ESMIA CONSULTANTS INC.	CA	
USMF	THE UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND FOUNDATION INC	US	
UMD	UNIVERSITY OF MARYLAND	US	
EPFL	ECOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FEDERALE DE LAUSANNE	CH	
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UNIBAS	UNIVERSITAT BASEL	CH	
Imperial	IMPERIAL COLLEGE OF SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE	UK	
Oxford	THE CHANCELLOR, MASTERS AND SCHOLARS OF THE UNIVERSITY OF OXFORD	UK	
UCL	UNIVERSITY COLLEGE LONDON	UK	

Executive Summary

This report provides the second update to the initial strategy for communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of the DIAMOND project that was published in deliverable D7.2 in May 2023. As in the initial report and its first update, this second update begins by defining the scope of communication, dissemination, and exploitation in the context of DIAMOND and by setting the CDE targets of the project. Additionally, the report sets quantifiable indicators for specific activities that will be monitored throughout the duration of the project, such as achieving 10 articles and press releases in the project's course.

Next, the report identifies the target audiences of the project as well as the promotional channels to reach them. The project audiences range from scientists/researchers/academia to decision-makers in policy/industry/NGOs, and civil society and will be further refined during the project. To reach these different audiences, a diverse selection of promotional channels is suggested. At the core of this strategy is the DIAMOND website, serving as the primary hub for information dissemination and providing access to all related promotional materials. Similarly, processes related to the continuous enhancement of the IAM PARIS platform to facilitate data harmonisation and modelling and foster the co-creation of assumptions, parameters, and scenarios, as well as host material related to the newly developed models, are briefly outlined. External communication channels are also envisioned to play an instrumental role in the project's CDE, including social media (e.g., X, LinkedIn, and Instagram), news websites and blogs (e.g., EURACTIV and The Conversation), events such as conferences and workshops, and synergies with other relevant projects.

The CDE plan also outlines the types of materials envisioned to promote the DIAMOND scope, objectives, and results through the identified channels. The visual identity and logo of the project have already been developed, based on the project's main messages of enhancing modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways. This visual identity is used in the design of the project website and promotional materials, including articles, infographics, videos, and presentations. Furthermore, project updates are distributed via the project's bi-monthly newsletters and partners' newsletters as well, which will further increase the project's visibility.

The plan concludes by detailing the advancement of promotional activities undertaken throughout the project, including the ongoing development and strategic use of social media channels (X, LinkedIn, Instagram), the dissemination of the project's objectives and progress through these platforms, and sustained engagement through participation in relevant events and conferences.

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1 Introduction

DIAMOND seeks to update, upgrade, and fully open six Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution, and geographic granularity. It further enhances modelling capacity to assess the feasibility and desirability of Paris-compliant mitigation pathways, their interplay with adaptation, circular economy, and other SDGs, their distributional and equity effects, and their resilience to extremes, as well as robust risk management and investment strategies.

This is done through the integration of tools and insights from psychology, finance research, behavioural and labour economics, operational research, and physical science. The project develops a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process and co-create research questions that stretch the frontiers of climate science, as well as establishes vibrant communities of practice to transparently open model enhancements and to develop capacities, thereby lowering the entrance barriers to the established IAM community.

DIAMOND aims to:

- produce iteratively updated, upgraded, open-source versions of six leading IAMs;
- further enhance the capabilities of IAMs to assess the trade-offs and co-benefits of a transition to climate neutrality with other SDGs;
- enable the systematic evaluation of interactions among climate change mitigation, adaptation, risks, physical impacts;
- validate the capacity of the enhanced IAMs to support climate and other development policies and COVID-19 recovery efforts at multi-level aspects;
- transparently open all modelling enhancements to the wider modelling community;
- develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to co-create the research questions, legitimise the implementation process and model development, and optimise the communication of project results.

This report describes the second update to the initial strategy for the communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) of information and results of DIAMOND to relevant audiences. Overall, the CDE plan has the following objectives:

1. Communicating project results and successful practices to demonstrate the project's impact to a wider audience, both online and in-person.
2. Creating the means to disseminate results to stakeholders, including policymakers, NGOs, industries, the scientific community, and even citizens, motivating them to exploit DIAMOND results.
3. Promoting the exploitation potential of the results for the six IAMs, both during and beyond the project life, through partners' networks and ongoing activities.

These objectives, along with other special requirements for DIAMOND, are described in detail in Chapter 2. In order to fulfil these objectives, the CDE plan also discusses the target audiences and their characteristics and outlines communication channels to share project results so that they are openly available and easily accessible to everyone. Additionally, the plan describes a list of methods tailored to each target group, such as communication materials, a visual identity, and social media packs for the general public, as well as external conferences and synergies and collaborations with other EU projects for academic dissemination.

In summary, the CDE plan is structured based on the following questions on the promotion process:

- **To whom?** Identification of the audiences to which the project will be promoted (Chapter 3).

- **How?** Analysis of potential promotional channels and selection of the most appropriate ones, according to the target audience and the message to be disseminated (Chapter 4).
- **What?** Planning and implementation of the CDE activities (Chapter 5 for activities that are already implemented and Chapter 6 for next steps on improving dissemination).

2 Goals and targets of the CDE plan

2.1 The three pillars of promotion: Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation

Communication is the process of informing the widest possible audience, including the media and the wider public, regarding the project and its results. Apart from establishing the branding of DIAMOND as a project about improving IAMs, communication efforts focus on promoting pertinent results and novel insights generated by the improved models, showcasing applications to EU policy benchmarks, national energy and climate plans, and strategies for businesses, energy-intensive industries, and financial institutions.

Dissemination is the process of transferring produced knowledge and results to enable others to use and exploit them. Dissemination focuses on the results of the initiative, rather than the initiative itself, as well on how the outcomes can be exploited by interested parties. The main audiences suitable for dissemination are the ones who could use the results in their operation. In the case of DIAMOND, these are 1) modellers working on IAMs and scenario analysis who could adopt the project's open-source improvements in their own models, 2) researchers working on climate change mitigation who could update their work through the project's outcomes, 3) policymakers at different levels (EU, national, and local policymakers), 4) industries which could exploit results to take more robust decisions in issues related to mitigation and adaptation, considering important but previously unexploited issues, 5) NGOs, civil society organisations and citizens, in general, who would be provided with insights on how small scale actions and lifestyle and behavioural changes could contribute to enhancing climate targets and what the benefits and burdens of these actions entail.

Exploitation is the effective practical use of project results through scientific, economic, political, or societal routes of utilisation. The objective of exploitation is to go one step further than dissemination and turn research and innovation actions into concrete value and impact for society. Thus, the main audiences of exploitation are the same as the ones suitable for dissemination.

2.2 Overall Targets

Creating a living document

The CDE plan is periodically updated throughout the project while we will also monitor all CDE activities. All CDE activities up to September 2025 are documented in this report. The WP7 team will make the required adjustments to the project's actions if there is a risk that the desired outcomes might not be met. The plan will be also continuously updated with feedback from stakeholders, following the overall CODESIGN methodology of the project (see WP2). This two-way communication will be especially prominent in the development and operation of the website and the new functionalities of the IAM PARIS platform.

Customising information to target audiences

The CDE strategy is taking into account a customised approach to successfully communicate the project's key messages to its various target groups based on the audience segmentation that is initially selected (see Chapter 3). Accordingly, the WP7 team is creating distinct core messages for each group and link them with appropriate communication channels. Each target audience has formal and informal channels for communication (e.g., scientific publications versus scientific groups in X and LinkedIn). Therefore, in addition to being mindful of the language used, it is important to consider communication style and tone. While the essential scientific content will stay unchanged, communication initiatives will be adapted for various stakeholder groups. Nevertheless, for the

sake of scientific relevance and integrity, the project findings will not be downplayed, even when conflicting with particular interests.

Adopting an inclusive and gender-sensitive approach

Gender is a focal point in DIAMOND as it is central in the formation, response, and responsibility bearing of the energy transition (e.g., see Fathallah & Pyakurel, 2020). Gender will be prominent in the CODESIGN (WP2) block of the project, both in terms of a continuous discussion theme among stakeholders in the contexts of where, when, and how gender issues should be represented in scenarios and models, but also by achieving a balanced gender representation in all knowledge co-production activities. Similarly, the WP7 team will ensure a good balance of stakeholders of different genders, ages, and backgrounds in its dissemination activities.

Planning for a restriction-resilient CDE

Due to uncertainties related to major global disturbances such as an eventual resurgence of COVID-19, appropriate methodological alternatives have been identified to ensure that the dissemination and communication activities are not brought to a complete standstill and DIAMOND can continue producing results. While online meetings and communication have become common during the last years, for the sake of building trust with the project team and with external stakeholders, physical events will still be used when possible. In cooperation with the project coordinator, the WP7 team will constantly monitor major global disturbances and decide when each methodological alternative will be used. Table 1 shows activities that are identified as potentially vulnerable to such disturbances, along with their methodological alternatives.

Table 1. DIAMOND activities that can be potentially affected by travelling restrictions

Activity	Preferred implementation	Methodological alternatives
Co-design activities	In-person workshops	Virtual workshops, carefully designed to reduce video-call fatigue and secure time for discussion and input from all participants
Annual project meetings among consortium partners	In-person meetings	Online meetings through MS Teams
Conferences, pitch meetings with policymakers, and other communication and dissemination activities	In-person and online activities	Only online (through MS Teams)
Final EU conference	In-person and online event	Only online, as a webinar (through MS Teams)

Going open access and paper-free

All content will be provided in open-access format. Regarding scientific publications, we will prioritise not only high-impact but also fully open-access journals offering, when feasible, open peer review, such as Open Research Europe which will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of

participating organisations. Access to papers and supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated Zenodo community¹, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability.

The CDE strategy is designed to be as paper-free content as possible, having at least an 80% digital communication and dissemination focus. Printed material will be used sparingly and only when deemed necessary to the CDE activity at hand. However, templates for printed material are provided on the website, allowing any interested party to download and use them.

2.3 Monitored CDE activities and indicators

To ensure that project results are successfully communicated, disseminated, and exploited, a set of targets and indicators has been set (Table 2). Progress towards these targets will be monitored on a regular basis, to confirm that the project is on track to achieve them or to take corrective measures if necessary (see Chapter 5 for the current progress). The communication channels and materials to achieve these targets are detailed in Chapter 4.

Table 2. CDE Indicators

Activity	Target	Means of verification / Dissemination channel
DIAMOND visual identity	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project to all stakeholder groups	Summary of all monitoring means
Enhanced IAM PARIS platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating data harmonisation and modelling. Fostering co-creation of assumptions, parameters, scenarios 2,000 unique users/year 40% of return visitors 	Google Analytics
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2,000 unique visitors per year 40% of return visitors 	Google Analytics account was set up when the website launched
Networking activities with EU projects under the same or relevant topics	Project reference in 20 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	Digital monitoring, No. of joint papers & acknowledged projects in papers
Social Media channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #climatediamond hashtag used 1,000 times on social media 500 followers on LinkedIn 	Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn own analytics
Commentaries, bi-monthly newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4,000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate 	Email monitoring system; Website download analytics
Infographics & videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 1500 views (videos) 400 downloads (infographics) 	YouTube/Instagram statistics; No. of downloads from the website
Blog posts, press releases, and articles on news sites	At least 10 articles and press releases in the project's lifetime	Media monitoring regularly, Copies of articles shared on the website
Policy briefs, business guides	6 briefs; 2 business guides	No. of briefs/ business guides
A final EU Conference	Audience of 70-100 people	No. of attendees; minutes; photos
Scientific outreach	> 50 papers; > 20 conferences	Digital monitoring

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/diamond/>

3 Target audiences

For achieving efficient and successful CDE activities, it is crucial to have a thorough awareness of the interests and motivations of the stakeholders that are considered as target audiences for the project. As DIAMOND aims to engage with diverse audiences, the WP7 team will aim to understand the characteristics of potentially interested parties, facilitate tailored communication, and implement different engagement strategies for each audience. Table 3 shows the target audiences that have been identified at the project's start, along with preferred communication methods for each audience.

Table 3. Target audiences and preferred communication methods

Target audiences	Preferred communication methods
Scientists/Researchers/Academia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications and project deliverables • Scientific conferences (e.g., IAMC and ECEMP conferences) • Social media posts • Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) • IAM PARIS platform
H2020 and Horizon Europe projects, European and international modelling consortia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in EU project clustering events • Participation in modelling conferences and meetings • Mailing lists and newsletters • IAM PARIS platform
Policymakers at all scales	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy briefs and commentaries • Pitch meetings • Policy-relevant conferences and events (e.g., COP meetings, EU Sustainable Energy Week, EU Green Week) • IAM PARIS platform
Industry decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business guides • Industry-relevant events • Social media posts • Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube) • IAM PARIS platform
Civil society and NGOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social media posts • News articles • Infographics and videos (shared via website and YouTube)
The media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press releases • News articles

Based on the experience of the WP7 team with previous Horizon projects relating to energy and climate topics (e.g., PARIS REINFORCE², IAM COMPACT³), an initial list of stakeholders has been identified for each of the target audience categories. The list has been further enhanced through the more than 53 stakeholders that have been registered in the DIAMOND Stakeholder Engagement Database (Milestone 3) and have agreed on receiving news about the project. In line with the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), exchanging sensitive information about the stakeholders between partner organisations in the consortium is avoided, unless explicit consent has been provided by a stakeholder. Each partner organisation will oversee establishing and maintaining contact with their own stakeholders for communication purposes, under the coordination of the WP7 team.

² <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820846>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10105630>

4 Promotional channels and means

At the heart of the DIAMOND CDE plan is the design and implementation of promotional channels and means to reach target audiences, disseminate messages and outputs, and ensure their exploitation. The promotional channels are the routes through which the messages may find the desired destinations, including the DIAMOND project website and the IAM PARIS platform, posts on social media, participation in conferences and others. The promotional means are the media that encapsulate the promoted message and distribute it via the proposed channels, i.e., publications, infographics, or videos.

Each combination of promotional channels and means has a particular function and level of promotion. For instance, a scientific publication contains technical details that aim to provide scientists, modellers, and researchers with a more in-depth view of the project's outcome. On the other hand, an infographic is better suited to showcase the project's concept and results to a broader audience, whereas a policy brief is expected to target policymakers.

4.1 Promotional channels

4.1.1 The DIAMOND website

The DIAMOND project's website⁴ serves as the centre of the promotional process. It is used for all three pillars of promotion and contains (or links to) every promotional material of the project. The website was developed during the first months of the project and came online in March 2023.

The website consists of the following sections and pages:

- The "About" section includes several pages on the project's description, namely its concept, objectives, work structure, and the synthesis of the scientific advisory board. This includes the "Project Consortium" page that showcases the synthesis of the consortium as well as the scientific capacity of the project partners, including links to their institutional websites.
- The "News & Events" page is used to promote all project activities, events, and significant results, while the "Communication" section of the website is dedicated to newsletters, videos, infographics, and media articles.
- The "Publications" section is used to store project deliverables, policy briefs, and business guides as well as scientific articles that acknowledge project funding.
- Lastly, the "Open science" section provides information about project synergies with other projects and modelling teams as well as presents the IAMs that will be upgraded during their project and lists their expanded capabilities. The section also includes a description and link to the IAM PARIS modelling platform that presents detailed model documentation and results of all modelling activities of the project (see Section 4.1.2 below for more information about the platform).

The website has been designed to maximise accessibility, reflecting the inclusive approach of DIAMOND. The website's colour palette is carefully curated to be in line with the DIAMOND logo and the overall visual identity. On the technical implementation, the website is developed using responsive web design, enabling access from different screen sizes and devices. Additionally, all content hosted on the website (e.g., infographics, deliverables,

⁴ <https://climate-diamond.eu>

and relevant material) is provided with open access. Regarding the open-access scientific publications (and in line with open-access provisions; see Chapter 2), details such as title, authors, and journal are provided on the website, as well as links (DOIs) to the publications, directing the user to the journal-hosted version of an article and the Zenodo repository hosting relevant data.

Aiming to increase its visibility, the website was and will be continuously promoted through the other communication and dissemination channels of the project, such as social media and newsletters. Moreover, several news items were already drafted to boost search engine optimisation and place the website at the top of search engine results for relevant queries. Along with the IAM PARIS platform, the project website will stay online for at least two years after the project ends and will be key to maintaining the visibility of achievements of the project.

Several design upgrades and improvements have already taken place since the launch of the website. The website has been enriched with new content such as news items as well as reports and photos from project-related events. The purpose of these images would be to illustrate the inter- and transdisciplinary working process of DIAMOND as well as highlight the multiple dimensions of the IAMs and the practical applications of modelling results. The WP7 team will always contact individuals featured in photos and will obtain their consent prior to publication.

4.1.2 The IAM PARIS platform

As a vessel to coordinate its climate-economy modelling activities, DIAMOND will further enhance and exploit the access to the IAM PARIS platform (<https://iamparis.eu>; formerly known as I²AM PARIS). IAM PARIS is an open-access, data exchange modelling platform developed in the context of the LC-CLA-01-2018 PARIS REINFORCE project (also coordinated by ICCS, part of NTUA). Much like DIAMOND, the platform is sustained by other H2020 (NDC ASPECTS⁵ and ENCLUDE⁶) and Horizon Europe (IAM COMPACT⁷ and TRANSIENCE⁸) projects. It is intended as a vessel for documenting IAMs, energy system models, and sectoral modelling capabilities, inputs, and outputs so that modelling exercises and their outcomes are made fully accessible and transparent to the research community, the policy world, and all other interested parties and stakeholders.

The platform will host the documentation of all modelling improvements of DIAMOND as well as the results of each modelling exercise, providing access to datasets and tailor-made visualisations, infographics, videos, policy briefs, and presentations. The platform will also function as a portal for promoting interactions among the different communities of practice and providing a common space to share inputs, definitions, and findings. In that way, the platform will facilitate data harmonisation and modelling and foster the co-creation of assumptions, parameters, and scenarios.

The platform is online but mainly contains the results and models from the PARIS REINFORCE⁹ and IAM COMPACT¹⁰ projects. In the context of DIAMOND, several new functionalities are currently underway in the platform, such as an extended suite of validation checks that can be used by project partners and other modelling teams to check their modelling results. More functionalities are planned for the fourth year of DIAMOND, as more research outcomes become available.

⁵ <https://ndc-aspects.eu/>

⁶ <https://encludeproject.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.iam-compact.eu/>

⁸ <https://www.transience.eu/>

⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/820846>

¹⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/10105630>

4.1.3 Social media

Social media are online forums and platforms to exchange/share thoughts, opinions, knowledge, and expertise with a large audience and can be also used to host marketing, advertising efforts, and promotional campaigns. Due to the project's focus on so many diverse target audiences, it is envisaged that social media are and will be extensively used to promote messages and results to the wider public and relevant stakeholder groups (see also Chapter 3). Moreover, social media could offer a channel for comprehensible and accessible communication with target audiences as well as provide links to more in-depth dissemination resources. In terms of social media platforms, WP7 teams will continue to focus on using X (formerly known as Twitter), LinkedIn, and Instagram. The goal and planning for each social media channel are shown in Table 5.

Table 4. Targets and plan per social media channel

Social Media	Purpose	Plan
X	Increase project's visibility in the scientific and policymaking community, as well as in the civil society	At least one post per week on the project's progress and relevant current affairs. Posts will be more frequent later in the project when more results will be delivered. News from project partners and members of the IAM community of practice are also reposted and shared.
LinkedIn	Increase project's visibility in the scientific, policymaking, and business community	Ad hoc posts on the project's progress with an emphasis on model/result applications (scientific, business, policy), as well as reposting and sharing information from project partners and members of the IAM community of practice.
Instagram	Increase project's visibility in the wider public	Around 1-2 post(s) per month, mostly in the form of illustrations, infographics, or stories

X (formerly known as Twitter) is an online social networking service in which users post and interact with short messages (less than 280 characters). It is ideal for short announcements of project outcomes. Via its X account¹¹, DIAMOND is envisaged to reach a wide range of diverse audiences.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a business and employment-oriented social network, that allows individuals and organisations to promote their professional progress and outcomes. The DIAMOND project's page¹² on LinkedIn is used to target more specialised audiences within the scientific, policymaking, and business community and provide more detailed information about project outcomes.

Instagram

Instagram¹³ is a social networking app for sharing photos and videos, and it is ideal for communicating short and

¹¹ <https://twitter.com/climatediamond>

¹² <https://www.linkedin.com/company/climatediamond/>

¹³ <https://instagram.com/climatediamond?igshid=YmMyMTA2M2Y=>

vivid messages to wide audiences. Our goal is to achieve more active involvement of citizens in climate action based on a better understanding and demonstration of how small-scale actions contribute to the achievement of large-scale climate policy objectives including through socially innovative approaches, and a better understanding of which actions/policies are more effective. This data will help us create more nuanced decision rules for IAMs on citizens' willingness to change unsustainable behaviours and adopt climate-conscious practices. Citizen-led practices with high mitigation potential will be also disseminated in an accessible and user-friendly format to all stakeholders (e.g., in Instagram feeds or videos), encouraging them to share and repost them. We will also share all methodologies and tools for public engagement that will be developed in the project with the wider modelling community, to promote their exploitation. Stories can be used to ask followers questions to get feedback on their willingness to change.

YouTube

YouTube¹⁴ will be used for hosting and promoting DIAMOND videos, including main outputs, project events and participation in workshops. To date, three videos have been successfully uploaded.

4.1.4 News websites and blogs

The following section presents a list of high-calibre media websites that can be contacted to communicate and disseminate project outputs to a wide audience. The list is indicative and non-exhaustive and will be modified or extended whenever necessary.

EURACTIV

EURACTIV¹⁵ is an independent pan-European media network specialised in EU policymaking, covering policy processes upstream of decisions. It provides free and localised news about EU policy in twelve languages, and together with its media partners reaches 1.7 million users across Europe and the rest of the world.

The Guardian

The Guardian¹⁶ is an acknowledged British daily newspaper founded in 1821 reaching a total of 24.9 million people each month. It features a section dedicated to the environment, with subtopics on climate change, wildlife, energy, and pollution. It is envisaged that the project's outcomes can be promoted via The Guardian to a wide variety of audiences fulfilling all three pillars of promotion.

The Conversation

The Conversation¹⁷ is an independent source of news, analysis, and expert opinion, written by academics and researchers and delivered directly to the public. It is estimated that its global audience is about 14.1 million readers per month. It is envisaged that project results can be promoted via The Conversation to audiences appropriate for dissemination and exploitation.

ClimateChangePost

ClimateChangePost¹⁸ features the latest news on climate change and adaptation with a special focus on Europe.

¹⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@climatediamond>

¹⁵ <https://www.euractiv.com/>

¹⁶ <https://www.theguardian.com/>

¹⁷ <https://theconversation.com/>

¹⁸ <https://www.climatechangepost.com/>

Many of its articles present the latest results from scientific publications and reports, making it an ideal conduit for DIAMOND to reach a wide range of its target audiences.

ClimateChangeNews.com

An international platform¹⁹ that covers climate change news, analysis, commentary, video, and podcasts focused on developments in global climate politics.

Euronews – Climate Now

For dissemination to a very wide audience, the Climate Now²⁰ programme of the Euronews channel may be a good fit for DIAMOND.

Energypost.eu

Energy Post²¹ provides an open platform to exchange and debate energy topics for policymakers, market players, analysts, and other stakeholders and could be used to reach specialised audiences for project results.

4.1.5 Magazines

Research*eu

Research*eu Results magazine²² covers topics of research interest in the EU. Through this magazine, results of DIAMOND can be communicated and disseminated to scientists, policymakers in the EU and Member States, and the general public.

4.1.6 Online collaboration and sharing platforms

Climatechangemitigation.eu

Climatechangemitigation.eu is a portal that collects and disseminates information from different EU-funded research projects on climate change mitigation. DIAMOND will use the portal²³ to promote its results to scientific and policymaking communities working on mitigation topics.

REScoop.eu

REScoop.eu²⁴ is a growing network of 1.900 European energy cooperatives and their 1.250.000 citizens who are actively participating in the energy transition. DIAMOND will use this channel to communicate and disseminate results but also recruit potential stakeholders for co-creation activities.

Energy Cities

Energy Cities²⁵ is a network of 1,000 local governments in 30 countries that establish a trustful dialogue between citizens, local leaders, and EU & national institutions to accelerate the energy transition in Europe. As with RESCOOP.eu, DIAMOND will contact Energy Cities to promote announcements related to the dissemination of

¹⁹ <https://climatechangenews.com/>

²⁰ <https://www.euronews.com/green/green-series/climate-now>

²¹ <http://energypost.eu/>

²² https://cordis.europa.eu/research-eu/home_en.html

²³ <http://climatechangemitigation.eu/>

²⁴ <https://www.rescoop.eu/news-and-events>

²⁵ <https://energy-cities.eu/>

project outcomes, but also to the recruitment of participants for its activities.

Capacity4Dev

Capacity4Dev²⁶ is the European Commission's knowledge-sharing platform for development cooperation aiming to improve capacity building. The platform has over 25,000 members who share, learn, and collaborate on the fields of sustainable development. This channel is ideal for dissemination and exploitation purposes since its members are scientists, industrialists, EU staff, sustainable development professionals in the EU, policymakers at the EU and global level, as well as members of civil society.

IISD SDG Knowledge Hub

The SDG Knowledge Hub²⁷ is an online resource centre for news and commentary regarding the implementation of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, including discussions on progress across all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). It is envisaged that our outcomes can be promoted via the IISD SDG Knowledge Hub to actors involved in sustainable development, such as policymakers, scientists, NGOs, industrialists, and civil society.

ECEEE

The European Council for an Energy Efficient Economy²⁸ is a non-profit, independent organisation dedicated to promoting energy efficiency in Europe. Since a major modelling improvement that DIAMOND will undertake relates to behavioural change towards reducing energy demand, ECEEE can be contacted to promote relevant outputs to policymakers, businesses, and NGOs related to energy efficiency.

4.1.7 Data repositories and platforms

Zenodo

Zenodo is a platform developed by CERN with the goal to provide an easy-access data repository for scientific data from all over the world and from every discipline. The DIAMOND Zenodo community²⁹ will form a central hub for providing open and unrestricted access to the project's publications and data.

GitHub

GitHub³⁰ is a platform for hosting open-source code, allowing extensive functionalities for version control and collaboration. GitHub will be used to host the code for new model functionalities that will be developed as part of DIAMOND³¹, as well as scripts and inputs that will be used in the project's modelling exercises.

OpenAIRE

OpenAIRE³² is a science-related portal, the mission of which is to provide unlimited, barrier-free, open access to research outputs financed by public funding in Europe. The use of OpenAIRE will enable DIAMOND, on one hand,

²⁶ <https://europa.eu/capacity4dev/>

²⁷ <http://sdg.iisd.org/>

²⁸ <https://www.eceee.org/>

²⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/diamond/?page=1&size=20>

³⁰ <https://github.com/>

³¹ <https://github.com/CLIMATE-DIAMOND>

³² <https://www.openaire.eu/>

to report more effectively and efficiently the scientific, and other, outcomes of the action and, on the other, to reach a wide community of scientists, policymakers, and stakeholders interested in EU-funded research in general.

European Open Science Cloud

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)³³ aspires to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with an open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes.

4.1.8 Partners' websites/blogs

Most consortium partners have websites featuring news on their research activities. On these websites, articles on the progress of DIAMOND and announcements on recent reports or upcoming events will be published. Partners' websites that had already published about the start of the project include the websites of ETH Zurich³⁴, HOLISTIC³⁵, and ICSS³⁶. Other partner websites that could be used in the future for dissemination and communication include the websites of BC3³⁷, CESAR³⁸, CICERO³⁹, CYI⁴⁰, EASMA⁴¹, COMILLAS⁴², ISINNOVA⁴³, SEURECO⁴⁴, UM⁴⁵, ESMIA⁴⁶, UMD⁴⁷, EPLF⁴⁸, UNIBAS⁴⁹, Imperial⁵⁰, Oxford⁵¹, and UCL⁵². Project activities could also be promoted through partners' social media accounts.

4.1.9 Peer-to-peer mailing lists

Peer-to-peer (P2P) mailing lists are subscription-based email services that enable individuals interested in specific topics to communicate with each other and exchange opinions and project results. P2P lists related to DIAMOND project-related topics such as energy, IAMs, transdisciplinarity, and climate change mitigation can be powerful means to reach audiences from academia, policymaking, and business since most subscribers are actively working in sectors affected by these topics. These lists will be used to disseminate the project's progress and output (newsletters, press releases, and general announcements) and invite subscribers to participate in DIAMOND's

³³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

³⁴ <https://ethz.ch/en.html>

³⁵ www.holisticsa.gr

³⁶ <https://www.iccs.gr/en/institute-of-communication-and-computer-systems/>

³⁷ www.bc3research.org

³⁸ <https://www.cesarecon.at/language/de/>

³⁹ www.cicero.oslo.no

⁴⁰ <https://www.cyi.ac.cy/>

⁴¹ www.e4sma.com

⁴² <https://www.comillas.edu/en/>

⁴³ <https://www.isinnova.org/about-2/history/>

⁴⁴ www.erasme-team.eu

⁴⁵ <https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/>

⁴⁶ <https://esmia.ca/>

⁴⁷ <https://www.umd.edu/>

⁴⁸ <http://www.epfl.ch>

⁴⁹ <https://www.unibas.ch/en.html>

⁵⁰ <http://www.imperial.ac.uk>

⁵¹ <https://www.ox.ac.uk/about>

⁵² <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/>

open events and webinars. Additionally, these mailing lists will be used to follow research and novelties from project-relevant fields.⁵³

4.1.10 External events

With the aim to effectively promote DIAMOND, partners will be encouraged to participate in events organised outside the consortium and promote preliminary and final results, both during and after the end of the project. This includes events organised by the European Commission as well as international conferences and workshop fields related to the project's scope. All partners will participate in the identification of relevant events.

Scientific conferences

DIAMOND partners will participate in scientific conferences to disseminate the project results to the scientific community. Additionally, conferences will be used to monitor relevant research in fields related to energy citizenship and other relevant topics. The following conferences have been assessed as relevant to the project:

- European Climate + Energy Modelling Platform (ECEMP)⁵⁴
- Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC)⁵⁵
- International Energy Workshop⁵⁶
- Energy Modeling Forum⁵⁷
- International Transdisciplinary Conference⁵⁸
- Sustainable Development of Energy, Water and Environment Systems (SDEWES) conference⁵⁹
- Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE)⁶⁰

Policy conferences

Along the duration of DIAMOND from December 2022 to November 2026, four sessions of the UNFCCC's Conference of the Parties (COP) had and will take place. These conferences offer great opportunities to reach out to policymakers, NGOs, industrialists, scientists, and other audiences and promote the project. In terms of European-specific conferences, the European Sustainable Development Week⁶¹ and the European Sustainable Energy Week⁶² will be policy-relevant fora for presenting the project's results.

Workshops and other events and media

A series of workshops with key stakeholder groups will take place in the context of the modelling work, to inform our activities and outcomes and ensure their relevance. These workshops will also serve as dissemination fora, where knowledge and information generated will be shared and discussed. A final EU conference will take place to inform policy, other stakeholders, and the broader modelling research community on the project's IAM

⁵³ <https://enb.iisd.org/email/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.ecemf.eu/ecemp/european-climate-and-energy-modelling-platform/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/annual-meetings/>

⁵⁶ <https://www.internationalenergyworkshop.org>

⁵⁷ <https://emf.stanford.edu>

⁵⁸ <https://akademien-schweiz.ch/en/current/events/itd-conference-2021/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.sdewes.org/>

⁶⁰ <https://www.eaere.org/>

⁶¹ <https://esdw.eu>

⁶² https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa.eu/index_en

improvements and advanced, sustainable mitigation pathways. Building on lessons learnt from the COVID-19 pandemic, most workshops in the context of the co-design nature of the DIAMOND project will be organised in a digital format. This will help to avoid the environmental and economic impact of travelling, while also circumventing potential travel restrictions due to pandemic-related restrictions, as well as reducing the time investment from the participants.

4.1.11 Synergies

Synergies with relevant projects can increase the outreach potential of the project's outputs and raise awareness among a broad spectrum of stakeholders. DIAMOND will contact projects of interest and co-organise synergetic activities such as participating in each other's events and cross-disseminating information and outputs through social media and project websites. DIAMOND has already established connections with the WorldTrans⁶³ sister project, where the project coordinator (Dr Cecilie Mauritzen) of WorldTrans has been invited to the DIAMOND Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) and vice versa. Additionally, the NTUA section of ICCS is coordinating the IAM COMPACT project, which is focusing on the same domain of climate change mitigation as DIAMOND and will run in parallel, offering many options for synergies between the projects. The DIAMOND website already contains a section on such synergistic activities⁶⁴.

In parallel with co-creation activities with other research projects, DIAMOND aims to enhance communities of practice for climate-economy modelling. We will establish active channels for two-way communication and synergies with existing modelling consortia and communities such as IAMC⁶⁵, GCAM Community, and IEA-ETSAP⁶⁶. We will go beyond the usual synergies among such communities by aiming to encourage an open-source development process for the project's improved IAMs with the collaboration of external modellers.

4.2 Branding and promotional materials

Several types of promotional materials are envisaged to promote the DIAMOND project scope, objectives, and results in different stages of the project. All promotional materials have a consistent and distinctive visual identity and have been created within the first six months of the project⁶⁷.

4.2.1 Visual identity and communication package

Visual identity and logo

A simple but distinctive and appealing visual identity (D7.1) has been developed at an early stage in the project. The logo was custom-made for DIAMOND, and its blue and yellow hues were chosen intentionally. Blue is the most universally appealing colour on the spectrum because of its non-polarising traits; it is usually used in corporate logos related to software, finance, and technology as it creates a sense of security while showing professionalism. Yellow shows optimism and enlightenment but also caution, while brands that are seeking to draw in consumers with youthful energy often utilise this colour. In addition, the project's relation with the six IAMs also be depicted on the logo, as the shapes are six in number, and all together create a diamond of models.

⁶³ <https://sites.google.com/met.no/worldtrans/home>

⁶⁴ <https://climate-diamond.eu/open-science/synergies/>

⁶⁵ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/>

⁶⁶ <https://iea-etsap.org/>

⁶⁷ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/visual-identity/>

(especially among non-experts).

4.2.2 Promotional materials

Blog posts, articles, and press releases

Articles on climate action and energy strategies in leading media websites and blogs will be disseminated via the promotional channels identified in Section 4.1. Additionally, press releases will be developed by the WP7 team, disseminated through the website's newsletter, and promoted to relevant media. All partners will support this process by suggesting media contacts at the national level and extending the list of interesting media targets. At least 10 articles and press releases are expected to be published during the project's course.

Scientific publications

Scientific publications are one of the key means of disseminating the project's results to the research community and building scientific credibility for the project's work. Scientific articles will be published in open-access, high-quality, peer-reviewed journals. Partners will also be encouraged and assisted in publishing their results in working paper series. These activities will ensure that the project and its results will be made known to the public at large. Journals also offering open peer review, such as Open Research Europe, will be considered as a possible outlet. In the case of hybrid or transformative journals, the gold open access option will be selected, and the APC will be immediately covered via institutional agreements of participating organisations. Access to papers and supporting datasets will be made immediately available in a dedicated project OpenAIRE/Zenodo community, using Creative Commons licenses for reusability and DOIs for findability. Moreover, the WP7 team will use its social media channels to promote the articles. A special issue is also envisioned using the consortium partners' connections to respective journal editors to further support the scientific dissemination and exploitation of the project's results.

DIAMOND newsletter

The newsletter's goal is to create awareness and involve stakeholders in progress. A regular electronic newsletter is issued providing information on the project development and events every 2-3 months. The newsletter will incorporate inputs from all partners on the progress and key outcomes of the project. Its key aim is to create awareness about the ongoing work of the action and involve stakeholders in progress. In compliance with the GDPR, a person will be included on the newsletter mailing list only if one is informed and explicit consent has been given, while the possibility of withdrawing the consent is clearly explained. Consent will be provided either by filling out an online subscription form or by direct email in case of personal contacts.

Press releases at partners' institutions

DIAMOND provides regularly the communication departments of all consortium partners with content to be processed for the partners' newsletters, websites, and other media channels.

5 Implemented activities as of September 2025

During the first 34 months of the project, several CDE activities have been implemented. Nevertheless, dissemination efforts are expected to intensify during the next year when most deliverables and scientific products of DIAMOND will be available. As of September 2025, 23 out of the 50 project deliverables have been finalised (including this report). For now, the WP7 team aimed to establish a strong presence on social media, creating weekly posts derived from the project’s concept and methodology. Figure 2 shows the project’s CDE tracker, including a selection of implemented activities. The tracker is used to monitor and document events and media activities of the project; it is available online⁷² and is frequently updated. The following sections show implemented activities in more detail.

Date	Responsible partner	Type of media activity (select from drop-down list)	Title media activity / Description	Country / Medium	N° of ppl reached	Scientific community									Dissemination level (local, regional, national, European...)
						Industry	Civil society	General public	Policy makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other (who)		
12/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, As competitive this duo (#Serbia and...)	N/a	135	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
		Social Media	Twitter Post, Day 1 of the @climatediamond kick-off meeting! This project will update, upgrade and fully open 6 IAMs that are emblematic in scientific and policy processes, improving their sectoral and technological detail, spatiotemporal resolution and geographic granularity. #climatediamond	N/a	410	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
15/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	451	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
15/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	Twitter Post, Day 2 of @climatediamond kick-off meeting. Today, we discussed about the challenges, opportunities, and near-term objectives concerning our project. Our partners presented their 6 IAMs and the expanding model capabilities. Stay tuned as there are more to come! #climatediamond	N/a	2,013	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
16/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	710	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
16/12/2022	HOLISTIC	Social Media	Twitter Post, In 2023, @climatediamond will kickstart its journey to update, upgrade & open 6 major #IAMs! We will develop a transdisciplinary scientific approach to legitimise the implementation process, co-create research questions and establish vibrant communities of practice. Stay tuned!	N/a	267	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
3/1/2023	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	326	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
3/1/2023	HOLISTIC	Social Media	Twitter Post, Introducing #climatediamond Consortium members: ICCS is @climatediamond's coordinator; will lead open science activities & model improvement & use (GCAM, PROMETHEUS, CLEWs). ICCS areas of expertise are the coordination of large modelling consortia; IAMs; co-creation & risk/uncertainty	N/a	348	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global
11/1/2023	HOLISTIC	Social Media	LinkedIn Post, Same as Twitter, See Above	N/a	427	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	Global

Figure 2. Screenshot of project tracker for CDE monitoring

5.1 Progress towards CDE indicators

Table 5. Progress towards CDE Indicators by Month 34

Activity	Target	Progress by Month
DIAMOND visual identity	Creating distinctiveness and appeal of the project to all stakeholder groups	Finished developing the visual identity of the project and the basic communication package

⁷² <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fUFBQVmq8JBrAVG7ENTi0YoxOqOJ8mAPU6oeElyMlhQ/edit?usp=sharing>

		(e.g., leaflets, poster, project presentation) ⁷³
Enhanced IAM PARIS platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating data harmonisation and modelling. Fostering co-creation of assumptions, parameters, scenarios 2,000 unique users/year 40% of return visitors 	DIAMOND scenarios and tools have not been uploaded yet. During model development, harmonisation guidelines were shared with modelling teams (see D3.2). All harmonisation details will be shared through the platform.
Project website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2,000 unique visitors per year 40% of return visitors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3300 unique visitors (Sep 2024 to Sep 2025) 10% return visitors
Networking activities with EU projects under the same or relevant topics	Project reference in 20 projects (websites, reports, etc.), joint papers and project meetings	20 joint publications with other projects ⁷⁴ and 2 joint presentations
Social Media channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> #climatediamond hashtag used 1,000 times on social media 500 followers on LinkedIn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 995 uses of the hashtag or project handle (including reposts) 658 followers on X 682 followers on LinkedIn 474 followers on Instagram
Commentaries, bi-monthly newsletters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4,000 recipients/downloads 30% opening rate 	1879 recipients, 39% opening rate
Infographics & videos	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > 1500 views (videos) 400 downloads (infographics) 	3 videos, 16 infographics
Blog posts, press releases, and articles on news sites	At least 10 articles and press releases in the project's lifetime	8 articles and press releases
Policy briefs, business guides	6 briefs; 2 business guides	No briefs or guides yet
A final EU Conference	Audience of 70-100 people	Will be organised towards the end of the project
Scientific outreach	> 50 papers; > 20 conferences	28 scientific publications acknowledging DIAMOND ⁷⁵ ; 45 conference presentations, posters, and sessions chaired (see Section 5.6)

5.2 Website

The DIAMOND project website is online since March 2023 and provides a comprehensive information portal about the project. It is also used as an archive of all activities of the project, including the first public deliverables, newsletter, and infographics. Currently, searching for “climate diamond” shows the website at the top 5 of Google search results, while traffic to the website has been mainly driven through the social media accounts of the project. In total, the website had around 3300 unique visitors within the last 12 months (September 2024-September 2025),

⁷³ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/visual-identity/>

⁷⁴ <https://climate-diamond.eu/open-science/synergies/>

⁷⁵ <https://climate-diamond.eu/publications/scientific-publications/>

achieving the target of 2000 visitors per year. However, returning visitors over the same period are only 10%, which is lower than the target of 40% that was set. A reason for this is that we had a surge of new visitors from the two webinars that have been organised in the context of WP6⁷⁶, especially for the second one on 17 June 2025 that attracted 459 new visitors within a day. Nevertheless, this number is expected to increase as more project products are developed and promoted on the website.

5.3 Social Media

The online presence of DIAMOND has been already established on X, LinkedIn, and Instagram. Specifically, an official DIAMOND account⁷⁷ has been created on X and has attracted 658 followers till now. Moreover, a LinkedIn organisation webpage⁷⁸ has been created to disseminate our actions and results to more business-oriented audiences and gained 682 users, achieving the KPI of 500 users. An Instagram account⁷⁹ has been also created and is used to disseminate visual material and infographics, featuring until now 474 followers. An impression of the items posted until now on X and LinkedIn is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. A selection of project posts in social media

5.4 Articles on other websites

Six partners have already referenced DIAMOND on their project websites (see Figure 4) and have already interacted with the project on social media. Additionally, the website of the Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium has also referenced the project⁸⁰. Other websites are expected to acknowledge the project such as the climatechangemitigation.eu portal. All references from other websites to DIAMOND are shown on the CDE tracker⁸¹.

⁷⁶ <https://climate-diamond.eu/news-events/>

⁷⁷ <https://twitter.com/climatediamond>

⁷⁸ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/climatediamond/>

⁷⁹ <https://www.instagram.com/climatediamond/?next=%2F>

⁸⁰ <https://www.iamconsortium.org/news-from-the-community/news-f-the-community/diamond-project/>

⁸¹ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fUFBQVm8JBMrAVg7ENTi0YoxOqOJ8mAPU6oeElyMlhQ/edit?usp=sharing>

IAMC
Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium
Founded 2007

THE CONSORTIUM SCIENTIFIC WORKING GROUPS

PROJECT

DIAMOND – Delivering the next generation of open Integrated Assessment Models for Net-zero, sustainable Development

Geographical scope: Global

Time horizon: December 2022 - November 2026

Initial Release: December 2022

Institution(s): Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), BC3 - Basque Centre for Climate Change, CESAR - Centre of Economic Scenario Analysis and Research, CICERO - CICERO Center for International Climate Research, CYI - The Cyprus Institute, 4SMA - Energy Engineering Economic Environment System Modelling and Analysis, HOLISTIC - HOLISTIC P.C., COMILLAS - Comillas Pontifical University of Madrid, ISINNOVA - Institute of Studies for the Integration of Systems, SEURECO - Société Européenne d'Économie, UM - Maastricht University, ESMIA - Energy Super Modelers and International Analysts, UMD - University of Maryland, EPFL - Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, ETH - Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zürich, UNIBAS - University of Basel, Imperial - Imperial College London, Oxford - University of Oxford, UCL - University College London

Link: <https://climate-diamond.eu/>

AA unibas.ch

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Suche Personen

Projects like DIAMOND need specific profiles and openness for new interdisciplinary research avenues

The Earth's climate is changing faster than at any point in the history of modern civilization, unequivocally as a result of human activities. At the University of Basel, researchers are actively engaged in collecting evidence to better understand human decision making in this context and to provide a scientific basis for urgent, fair and

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kortlevede klimadriveres effekt på klimaet og deres rolle i hvordan begrense klimaendringene, så vel som muligheter og utfordringer for å begrense klimaendringene i lys av sosiale, politiske og teknologiske begrensninger. Vi er særlig interessert i hvordan scenarier lages og brukes og alternative metoder for å kommunisere viktig innsikt fra scenarioanalyse. Nøkkelprosjekter inkluderer Paris Reinforce, IAM COMPACT, DIAMOND, ESM2025 og PROVIDE.

Vi legger stor vekt på å presentere funnene til et bredt publikum og på en forståelig måte.

Medlemmer av gruppen

Glen Peters
Forsker I

Jan S. Fuglestedt
Forskningsleder/Spesialrådgiver

AA erasme-team.eu

SEURECO ERAZME

DIAMOND, un nouveau projet de recherche Horizon Europe

La réunion de lancement du nouveau projet de recherche DIAMOND a eu lieu à Athènes le 15 et 16 décembre 2022

SEURECO participe à un nouveau projet Horizon Europe sur le développement et

ETH zürich Cultural studies of science

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DIAMOND

Overview

Our group is part of the newly funded EU project "Delivering the next generation of Open Integrated Assessment Models for net-zero, sustainable development" (DIAMOND).

The interplay among climate mitigation, adaptation and between climate action and other development agendas, including sustainable resource use, requires an integrated ecosystem of disciplines, methods, and tools. Despite the significant evolution

Figure 4. References of DIAMOND on other websites

5.5 Scientific publications

Despite that, most research outputs of the project will be released later in its duration, 28 scientific publications articles have been already published acknowledging DIAMOND. Articles published in scientific journals used the Gold Open Access option and are thus directly and freely accessible to the public.

Overall, the following published articles have acknowledged DIAMOND:

1. Buck, H. J., Al Khourdajie, A., Asayama, S., & Geden, O. (2025). Four scenarios for an IPCC navigating Artificial Intelligence. Research Division EU/Europe, Working Paper Nr. 08/2025, September 2025. https://www.swp-berlin.org/publications/products/arbeitspapiere/WP_Geden_etal_IPCC_290925.pdf (working paper)
2. Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Koasidis, K. & Van de Ven, D. J. (2025). GCAM-Europe v7. 2.0: Enhancing Policy-Relevant Climate Modelling Through Spatial and Sectoral Detail. EGUsphere, 2025, 1-

32. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-3546> (preprint under review)
3. Al Khourdajie, A., Gambhir, A., Keppo, I., Frilingou, N., Mittal, S., van de Ven, D. J., ... & Nikas, A. (2025). Navigating the unexpected: The impact of disruptive events on mitigation scenarios. <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7427967/v1> (preprint under review)
 4. Engel, L., Kukowski, C. A., & Hahnel, U. J. (2025). Empowering change: A self-control perspective on how choice architecture interventions can promote sustainable behavior change. *Motivation Science*. <https://doi.org/10.1037/mot0000396>
 5. Al Khourdajie, A. (2025). The role of artificial intelligence in climate change scientific assessments. *PLOS Climate*, 4(9), e0000706. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000706>
 6. Koasidis, K., Soursos, A., Xexakis, G., Labella, Á., Karamaneas, A., & Nikas, A. (2025). APOLLO-Live: A multi-criteria-based webtool for synchronous group decision making and consensus support in energy and climate policy deliberations. *Open Research Europe*, 5(88), 88. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.19614.3>
 7. Serebriakova, A. S., Polzin, F., & Sanders, M. (2025). Effects of Monetary Policy Rates on Energy Technologies: Implications for the European Green Transition. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/316394> (working paper)
 8. Zisarou, E., Fragkos, P., Van De Ven, D. J., Mittal, S., Frilingou, N., Rodés-Bachs, C., ... & Nikas, A. (2025). A window of (missed) opportunity? A comprehensive stocktake and energy-system impact assessment of global COVID-19 recovery packages. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 127, 104216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2025.104216>
 9. Sandstad, M., Steinert, N. J., Baur, S., & Sanderson, B. M. (2025). METEORv1. 0.1: A novel framework for emulating multi-timescale regional climate responses. *EGUsphere*, 2025, 1-49. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-1038> (preprint under review)
 10. van de Ven, D. J., Mittal, S., Nikas, A., Xexakis, G., Gambhir, A., Hermwille, L., ... & Peters, G. P. (2025). Energy and socioeconomic system transformation through a decade of IPCC-assessed scenarios. *Nature Climate Change*, 15(2), 218-226. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41558-024-02198-6>
 11. Pye, S., Bradshaw, M., Price, J., Zhang, D., Kuzemko, C., Sharples, J., ... & Dodds, P. E. (2025). The global implications of a Russian gas pivot to Asia. *Nature Communications*, 16(1), 386. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-55697-7>
 12. Beath, H., Mittal, S., Lamboll, R., & Rogelj, J. (2025). An exploration and evaluation framework for climate change mitigation scenarios with varying feasibility and desirability. *Environmental Research Letters*. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/addd35>
 13. Calcaterra, M., Aleluia Reis, L., Fragkos, P., Briera, T., de Boer, H. S., Egli, F., ... & Tavoni, M. (2024). Reducing the cost of capital to finance the energy transition in developing countries. *Nature Energy*, 1-11.
 14. Nikas, A. (2024). Projecting progress in sustainable development goals vis-à-vis climate action in climate-economy models. *PLOS Clim* 3(7): e0000449. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000449>
 15. Perdana, S., & Vielle, M. (2024). Industrial European regions at risk within the Fit for 55: How far implementing CBAM can mitigate?. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 100088.
 16. Sampedro, J., Van de Ven, D. J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Frilingou, N., Nikas, A., ... & Yarlagadda, B. (2024). Energy system analysis of cutting off Russian gas supply to the European Union. *Energy Strategy*

Reviews, 54, 101450.

17. Joshi, S., Zakeri, B., Mittal, S. *et al.* Global high-resolution growth projections dataset for rooftop area consistent with the shared socioeconomic pathways, 2020–2050. *Sci Data* **11**, 563 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03378-x>
18. Moreno, J., Campagnolo, L., Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Gonzalez-Eguino, M., Perdana, S., Van de Ven, D.-J., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Gargiulo, M., Herbst, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Neuner, F., Le Mouël, P., & Vielle, M. (2024). The impacts of decarbonization pathways on Sustainable Development Goals in the European Union. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-024-01309-7>
19. McGookin, C., Süsser, D., Xexakis, G., Trutnevyte, E., McDowall, W., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Few, S., Andersen, P. D., Demski, C., Fortes, P., Simoes, S. G., Bishop, C., Rogan, F., & Ó Gallachóir, B. (2024). Advancing participatory energy systems modelling. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 52, 101319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101319>
20. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2024). Three different directions in which the European Union could replace Russian natural gas. *Energy*, 130254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2024.130254>
21. Boitier, B., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzi, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, D.-J. van de Ven, Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU's path to net zero. *Joule*, 7(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joule.2023.11.002>
22. Perdana, S., Vielle, M., & Oliveira, T. D. (2024). The EU carbon border adjustment mechanism: Implications on Brazilian energy intensive industries. *Climate Policy*, 24(2), 260–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2023.2277405>
23. Koutsandreas, D., Trachanas, G. P., Pappis, I., Nikas, A., Doukas, H., & Psarras, J. (2023). A multicriteria modeling approach for evaluating power generation scenarios under uncertainty: The case of green hydrogen in Greece. *Energy Strategy Reviews*, 50, 101233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2023.101233>
24. Bailie, A., Pied, M., Vaillancourt, K., Bahn, O., Koasidis, K., Gambhir, A., Wachsmuth, J., Warnke, P., McWilliams, B., Doukas, H., & Nikas, A. (2023). Co-creating Canada's path to net-zero: A stakeholder-driven modelling analysis. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 4, 100061. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100061>
25. Koutsellis, T., Xexakis, G., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Karamaneas, A., Nikas, A., & Doukas, H. (2023). In-Cognitive: A web-based Python application for fuzzy cognitive map design, simulation, and uncertainty analysis based on the Monte Carlo method. *SoftwareX*, 23, 101513. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2023.101513>
26. Gambhir, A., & Nikas, A. (2023). Seven key principles for assessing emerging low-carbon technological opportunities for climate change mitigation action. *PLOS Climate*, 2(7), e0000235. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pclm.0000235>
27. Perdana, S., & Vielle, M. (2023). Carbon border adjustment mechanism in the transition to net-zero emissions: Collective implementation and distributional impacts. *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 25(3), 299–329. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10018-023-00361-5>

28. Cassetti, G., Elia, A., Gargiulo, M., & Chiodi, A. (2023). Reinforcing the Paris Agreement: Ambitious scenarios for the decarbonisation of the Central Asian and Caspian region. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Transition*, 3, 100048. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rset.2023.100048>

5.6 Events

DIAMOND project has organised a side event at the UNFCCC's 28th Conference of the Parties (COP 28) in Dubai. The event was organised in the Greek Pavillion at COP28 and was moderated by the DIAMOND consortium member Prof. Ryna Yiyun Cui, (*University of Maryland, US*). The agenda included the following interventions, also by members of the DIAMOND consortium:

- “Paving the way to net zero in the EU: key technologies, strategic decisions, and a roadmap” Speaker: Haris Doukas, *Professor at the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), President of the Society for the Environment and Cultural Heritage (ELLET) Energy Council, Mayor of the Municipality of Athens, Greece.*
- “Defining ‘Abated Fossil Fuels’ and identifying their role in the EU’s long-term ambition” Speaker: Alaa Al Khourdajie, *Research Fellow at the Department of Chemical Engineering of Imperial College London (Imperial)*
- “The role of gas in the EU’s net-zero trajectory: thinking in the context of the energy crisis” Speaker: Steve Pye, *Assoc. Professor at the UCL Energy Institute (University College London)*

Figure 5. Flyer from the side-event organised by DIAMOND at COP28

In terms of scientific conferences, the following presentations and posters have acknowledged DIAMOND:

1. Xexakis, G., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. “Cities at the forefront: current modelling practices and opportunities for integrated assessment models—insights from Athens, Greece”. 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. [presentation]
2. Xexakis, G., Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. “Modern software engineering practices for open and efficient integrated assessment modelling”. 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. [poster]
3. Frilingou, N., Van de Ven, D., Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Mittal, S., Torne, A., Trutnevyte,

- E., Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. (2025). Comparing cost-optimal to policy-driven scenarios for a decarbonised European energy system, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil. [presentation]
4. Rodés-Bachs, C., et. al., Health impacts and socioeconomic inequalities of future outdoor air pollution in Europe, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [presentation]
 5. Rouhette, T., et. al., Towards fire-resilient mitigation pathways in the AFOLU sector: modelling burned area and fire emission feedbacks in integrated assessment models, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [presentation]
 6. Van de Ven, D-J., et. al., GCAM-Europe: Enhancing Policy-Relevant Climate Modelling Through Spatial and Sectoral Detail, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster]
 7. Rodés-Bachs, C., et. al., Open Science Practices in Integrated Assessment Models, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster]
 8. Sampedro, J., et. al., rhap: A tool to analyze health impacts attributable to household air pollution, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster]
 9. Sampedro, J., et. al., Evaluating inter- and intra-regional air pollution inequalities in a decarbonized world, 18th IAMC Annual Meeting, November 11-13, 2025, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil [poster]
 10. Briers, S., Vienni-Baptista B., Koasidis, K., Peters, G., Mittal, S., Butnar, I., ... & Nikas, A. "Co-Designing Stakeholder-Informed Research Questions: A Transdisciplinary Approach for Integrated Assessment Modelling", European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation]
 11. Frilingou, N., Van de Ven, D-J., Sampedro, J., Horowitz, R., Rodés-Bachs, C., Mittal, S., Torne, A., Trutnevyte, E., Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. "Comparing cost-optimal to policy-driven scenarios for a decarbonised European energy system". European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation]
 12. Xexakis, G., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Frilingou, N., Sarmas, E., Marinakis, V., Doukas, H. "Cities at the forefront: current modelling practices and opportunities for integrated assessment models—insights from Athens, Greece". European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation]
 13. Vielle, M., & Perdana, S. "Regional Inequality of the European ETS-2". European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation]
 14. Perdana, S., & Vielle, M. "Integrating Spatial Granularity into Climate Policy Analysis: A CGE–GIS Framework for the European Union". European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum (ECEMP), October 16 – 17, 2025, Brussels, Belgium. [presentation]
 15. Nikas, A., Van de Ven, D-J., Rodes-Bachs, C., Rouhette, T., Horowitz, R., Sampedro, J., Frilingou, N., Georgiou, K., Zhao, X., Chaudhary, A., Koasidis, K. "Optimising sectoral climate mitigation efforts against multiple sustainability indicators: a multi-objective integrated assessment", 34th European Conference on Operational Research (EURO), July 22-25, 2025, Leeds, United Kingdom. [presentation]
 16. Koasidis, K., Soursos, A., Xexakis, G., Karamaneas, A., & Nikas, A. "A multi-criteria group decision making and consensus reaching webtool for synchronous deliberations using 2-tuple TOPSIS", 34th European Conference on Operational Research (EURO), July 22-25, 2025, Leeds, United Kingdom. [presentation]

17. Boitier, B., Mekki, H., Le Mouël, P. Estimating climate damage functions by type of damage for EU countries. 30th Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists, 16 - 19 June 2025, Bergen, Norway. [presentation]
18. Frilingou, N. et al. Regional impacts of energy technologies' cost of capital on decarbonisation. 30th Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists, 16 - 19 June 2025, Bergen, Norway. [presentation]
19. Briers, S., & Vienni-Baptista, B. (2025). Co-designing Integrated Assessment Models for net-zero sustainable development. Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [poster]
20. Herbig, V., Briers, S., & Vienni-Baptista, B. (2025). From Stakeholder Engagement to Inclusivity: Advancing Participatory Modeling for Net-Zero Sustainable Development. Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [poster]
21. Koasidis, K., Soursos, A., Xexakis, G., Karamaneas, A., & Nikas, A. "Enhancing Stakeholder Engagement for a Just Transition: An Operational Research Approach to Participatory Decision-Making", Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [presentation]
22. Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Zachmann, G., Mittal, S., van de Ven, D., -J., Horowitz, R., ... Koasidis, K., Nikas, A. "Advancing participatory integrated assessment modelling via a Policy Response Mechanism: a novel approach to policy-relevant, stakeholder-driven modelling", Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [presentation]
23. Tigka, C., Koasidis, K., Ruß, M., Hermwille, L., Rizos, V., Righetti, E., ... & Nikas, A. "Stakeholder insights and socio-technical perspectives for analysing sustainable transitions in energy-intensive industrial regions", Fifth Swiss Social Sciences and Humanities Energy Research Workshop (SSH Energy), June 16-17, 2025, Zurich, Switzerland. [presentation]
24. Sandstad, M., Sanderson, B., & Steinert, N. (2025). METEOR: A novel framework for emulating multi-timescale regional climate responses, EGU General Assembly 2025. [presentation]
25. Vienni-Baptista, B. (2024). Daylight in the service of SDGs: exploring methods for interdisciplinary collaboration. Daylight in the service of Sustainable Development Goals: a colourful spectrum of opportunities, Annual Conference, Daylight Academy and Velux Stiftung (Switzerland), Trondheim, Norway, 30-31 May, 2024. [presentation]
26. Sampedro, J., Khan, Z., Mittal, S., Kikstra, J. (2024). Incorporating equity, gender, health and other co-benefits into NEXUS and IAM research, EGU General Assembly 2024 [ITS3.27/ERE6.6 session]
27. Herbig, V., Briers, S., and Vienni-Baptista, B. (2024). From Stakeholder Engagement to Inclusivity: Advancing Participatory Modeling for Net-Zero Sustainable Development, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-9297, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-9297>, 2024. [presentation]
28. García-Muros, X., Alonso-Epelde, E., González-Eguino, M., and Rodríguez-Zúñiga, A. (2024). Can energy and environmental taxation be progressive in the EU?, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-10785, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-10785>, 2024. [presentation]
29. Van de Ven, D.-J. and Sampedro, J. (2024). Passenger transport decarbonisation under different equity considerations, EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-19615,

- <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-19615>, 2024. [poster]
30. Frilingou, N., van de Ven, D.-J., Mittal, S., Karamaneas, A., Nikolakakis, T., Gardumi, F., Koasidis, K., and Nikas, A. (2024). How do interest rates affect decarbonisation pathways? A stakeholder-driven multi-model analysis., EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria, 14–19 Apr 2024, EGU24-17148, <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-17148>, 2024. [poster]
 31. Alonso-Epelde, E., Rodés, C., and Moyano-Reina, M. (2024). MEDUSA – Modelling Equity and DistribUtional impacts for Socioeconomic Analysis. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-5065>, 2024. [poster]
 32. Vienni-Baptista, B. (2024). Pathways to inter- and transdisciplinary research for sustainable futures: opportunities and challenges. Vienna Doctoral School of Ecology and EvoluBon (VDSEE), Annual VDSEE Symposium, University of Vienna, Austria, February 16th, 2024. [keynote speak]
 33. Rhodes., C.B., et al. (2023). gcamreport: An R tool to Process and Standardise GCAM Outputs. 2023 GCAM Annual Meeting, June 6-8, 2023 (online) [poster]
 34. Sampedro, J. et al. (2023). Residential Energy Demand, Emissions, and Expenditures at Regional and Income-decile Level for Alternative Futures. 2023 GCAM Annual Meeting, June 6-8, 2023 (online) [poster]
 35. van de Ven, D.J., et al. (2023). Implementation of Current Policies in GCAM. 2023 GCAM Annual Meeting, June 6-8, 2023 (online) [poster]
 36. Nikas, A., Frilingou, N., Heussaff, C., Fragkos, P., Mittal, S., Sampedro, J., Giarola, S., Sasse, J.-P., Rinaldi, L., Doukas, H., Gambhir, A., Giannousakis, A., Golinucci, N., Koasidis, K., Rocco, M. V., Trutnevyte, E., Xexakis, G., Zachmann, G., Zisarou, E., ... Van de Ven, D.-J. (2023). Three corner options for replacing Russian gas imports in Europe: a multi-model analysis. IAMC 2023. [presentation]
 37. van de Ven, D.-J., Nikas, A., Gambhir, A., Koasidis, K., Elia, A., Al-Dabbas, K., Alibaş, Ş., Campagnolo, L., Chiodi, A., Delpiazzo, E., Doukas, H., Fougeyrollas, A., Gargiulo, M., Mouël, P. L., Neuner, F., Perdana, S., Ven, , Vielle, M., Zagamé, P., & Mittal, S. (2023). A multi-model analysis of the EU's path to net zero. IAMC 2023. [presentation]
 38. Perdana, et al. (2023). "Mapping the transition: Industrial European regions at risk within the fit for 55". Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [presentation]
 39. Zhang et al. (2023). "The shifting geopolitics of natural gas: Russia's invasion of Ukraine and implications for the low-carbon transition". Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [presentation]
 40. Xexakis et al. (2023). "The impacts of a polycrisis on sustainable development: Experts' vs. modellers' expectations and the capabilities of IAMs". Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [poster]
 41. Koasidis et al. (2023). "Delving in the impact of stakeholder input in modelled pathways: Canada's path to net-zero and the role of game-changing innovations". Sixteenth Annual Meeting of the Integrated Assessment Modeling Consortium (IAMC), November 14 - 16, 2023, Venice, Italy. [poster]
 42. Boitier, B. et al. (2023). A multi-model assessment of the EU's path to net zero: aligning near-term action with long-term visions. ECEMP 2023. [presentation]
 43. Frilingou, N. et al. (2023). A multi-model assessment of European strategies to eliminate Russian gas imports. ECEMP 2023. [presentation]

44. Vielle M. and Perdana. S. (2023). Mapping the transition: Industrial European regions at risk within the fit for 55. ECEMP 2023. [presentation]
45. Xexakis G. (2023). Dependency & Energy Security. ECEMP 2023. [session chair]

Additionally, 10 internal events have already been organised by the DIAMOND team, including general meetings and meetings between the modelling teams of the project (see Figure 6 for screenshots from these meetings). Details about the major meetings can be found on the website⁸² while the full list of events can be found on the dissemination tracker⁸³. In the coming years, DIAMOND partners are expected to organise and participate in even more events, helping to build communities of practice in climate modelling and to promote project results.

Figure 6. Photos from events that DIAMOND has participated in as of May 2024

Finally, in the context of WP6, DIAMOND has organised the following webinars for the modelling community (see Figure 7 for screenshots of their banners):

1. **Stakeholder Participation in IAMs:** In February 2025, the project DIAMOND organized a webinar on “Demystifying stakeholder participation in integrated assessment modelling and scenarios”. The webinar was especially intended for modellers using, as well as social scientists working with, IAMs and other climate-economy models, and aimed to provide an opportunity for exchanging practices and sparking potential synergies and initiatives on the topic.
2. **The past and future of scenarios in the IPCC:** DIAMOND project organized a webinar on “The past and future of scenarios in the IPCC” on Tuesday, 17 June 2025. This webinar was intended for researchers engaged in climate scenario development and assessment, especially those working with IAMs, energy-economy models, and broader scenario exercises. It provided a space to reflect on how scenarios had developed over time, explored opportunities to expand the modelling and scenario landscape, and considered how a more inclusive and pluralistic approach could enrich future assessments.

⁸² <https://climate-diamond.eu/news-events/>

⁸³ <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1fUFBQVm8JBMrAVg7ENTi0YoxOqOJ8mAPU6oeElyMlhQ/edit?usp=sharing>

Figure 7. Banners from the two DIAMOND WP6 webinars

Additionally, DIAMOND participated in the “Seminar Series 2025 #3” (Figure 8), which is part of the monthly seminars from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP), with colleagues from CICERO presenting the METEOR model to more than 30 participants.

Figure 8. DIAMOND in the CMIP seminar series, presenting the METEOR model

5.7 Synergies

Several synergies have already been established between DIAMOND and relevant European projects⁸⁴. The majority of the 28 journal publications that are currently acknowledging DIAMOND have been published as a synergy with other projects, most notably, the Horizon 2020 PARIS REINFORCE and the Horizon Europe IAM COMPACT. Additionally, on 17 April 2024, DIAMOND co-organised along with its sister project WorldTrans a presentation on the design of an interactive policy platform for climate change mitigation and adaptation. The meeting also included a discussion on further synergies between WorldTrans and DIAMOND (Figure 9).

⁸⁴ <https://climate-diamond.eu/open-science/synergies/>

Figure 9. Example of synergies between WorldTrans and DIAMOND (discussed during April 2024)

DIAMOND also participated in the MAIA Multiply programme, organised by the Horizon Europe MAIA project⁸⁵ which served as an aggregator and amplifier of the results of Horizon projects on climate topics (see Figure 10 for an example). MAIA also provided networking opportunities and CDE advice to participating projects, further increasing the impact of DIAMOND to its target audience. Since MAIA has already concluded by September 2025, DIAMOND has been included in the interactive synergy map of Climate Research Communication Network and has already participated in joint webinars and could pursue more science communication-related synergies during its last year⁸⁶.

Figure 10. The MAIA multiply program that DIAMOND is participating in

Finally, various DIAMOND partners participated in the final event of IAM COMPACT which took place in August 2025 in the Acropolis Museum in Athens, presenting findings from synergistic exercises as well as the overall approach of the project.

⁸⁵ <https://maia-project.eu>

⁸⁶ <https://www.esm2025.eu/science-policy-partnership/climate-research-communication-network/>

5.8 Newsletters and press releases

By the end of September 2025, the dissemination team of DIAMOND has sent ten newsletters and seven press releases in English, targeting 1879 English-speaking recipients. Newsletters were typically released after significant project events and provided updates and website links to all recent activities and outputs of DIAMOND, such as conferences, workshops, and scientific publications. Press releases were kept mainly for significant announcements that warranted a separate, dedicated release to showcase them. For more details on the contents of each newsletter and press release, see our website⁸⁷. Indicative screenshots of newsletters and press releases are included in Figure 11 below.

The implemented strategy has so far resulted in a higher than anticipated opening rate (39%), validating that the topics sent are of interest to the community, without overburdening the recipients. With the delivery of the first versions of the models (as illustrated in the latest press release; September 2025), as well as the progressive delivery of the final versions of the models and the scenario exercises, more opportunities for additional material are expected.

Figure 11. Indicative screenshots of the DIAMOND newsletter

5.9 Infographics and videos

Infographics have been developed catching the pulse of the FIFA World Cup 2022 and building up audience for project social media accounts. We produced several infographics showcasing the greenhouse gas emissions of countries participating in the World Cup. Figure 12 shows an example, while all infographics are available on the

⁸⁷ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/newsletters-press-releases/>

project website⁸⁸. More infographics will be developed when more project materials become available.

The upcoming delivery of the final versions of the models, and their use on scenario exercises will be exploited to deliver technical briefs which can then be converted into dedicated infographics.

Figure 12. Infographics for FIFA World Cup 2022

As explained in Section 4.1.3, DIAMOND maintains an active account on YouTube, uploading videos from the webinars organised and described in Section 5.3. Links to these videos are also provided in the project's website⁸⁹, which additionally includes videos from further sources related to DIAMOND participation (Figure 13). So far, four videos have been uploaded:

- A brief DIAMOND introduction
- The "Demystifying stakeholder participation in integrated assessment modelling and scenarios" webinar
- The "The past and future of scenarios in the IPCC" webinar
- The presentation of the METEOR model from the CMIP seminar.

⁸⁸ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/infographics/>

⁸⁹ <https://climate-diamond.eu/communication/videos/>

Marit Sandstad - CMIP Seminar April 2025

DIAMOND Home About News & Events Open Science Publications Communication Contact

Figure 13. Videos from the: a) METEOR presentation on the CMIP seminar; and b-c) the two webinars organised.

6 Next steps and final event

Throughout the duration of DIAMOND, the primary objective of the CDE plan has been to establish a strong project identity and online presence by developing its visual branding and website, building a solid social media following, and producing initial communication materials—such as event updates and publication highlights. This goal has been successfully achieved, as evidenced by the current size of the project’s audience on LinkedIn (682 followers, exceeding the KPI of 500), Instagram (474 followers), and X (658 followers), along with 3,300 unique website visitors recorded over the past 12 months (surpassing the KPI of 2,000 visitors). Dissemination could further ramp up during the final months of the project in order to attain the intended CDE performance, for instance, improving the rate of returning visitors (currently 10% against a target 40%). Additionally, DIAMOND has built its networks with significant modelling consortia (e.g., IAMC, ECEMP, and the GCAM community) and relevant projects (e.g., IAM COMPACT, TRANSIENCE), leading to publications developed as synergies between DIAMOND and these projects. It is expected that these collaborations will amplify in the coming years as more scientific outputs and, thus, more opportunities for synergies will become available.

In addition to the growing availability of the content for dissemination, the WP7 team aims to take the following actions to further improve the CDE performance of the project:

Website: More content will be included in the coming months, such as deliverables, publications, videos, and infographics. All project deliverables will be made publicly available during the final year of the project. In addition, over the coming months, new content will be released—including deliverables, publications, videos, and infographics—to highlight the project's progress and key outcomes.

Social media: The WP7 team will continue to post at least once a week on social media. This dissemination is expected to intensify as research outcomes of the project become available. The WP7 team will also become more active on Instagram by developing and posting visual material and infographics that promote the project and its outcomes. Expanding social media impact is a priority, with a focus on launching coordinated thematic campaigns around key milestones such as model releases and major publications. These campaigns will use visual content, strategic partner tagging, and active community engagement to drive interaction and follower growth. On Instagram, increasing the frequency of posts through weekly visuals and stories, along with the introduction of interactive features such as polls and Q&As, will help raise awareness and deepen engagement among broader audiences.

Media: Along with efforts to intensify social media presence, the WP7 team will produce at least 10 articles for media outlets and blogs. The articles will be based on the research outputs of the project and will aim to both increase awareness about DIAMOND and its goals and also contribute to attracting audiences beyond academia and research. The online presence of DIAMOND will be further strengthened in the upcoming period. This effort is expected to increase traffic to the project website and improve its search engine optimisation (SEO) through enhanced backlinking. Published articles will cover topics related to key DIAMONDS deliverables, focusing on content that is both engaging and relevant to a broader audience—including the final outcomes of the project.

Publications: Building on the project's 28 scientific papers produced by September 2025, publications are expected to be increased with the delivery of the models (methodological advancement papers; at least 20 such papers in total) and the scenario exercises (policy-relevant papers; at least 10 such papers in total) during the final year of the project.

Policy Briefs and Business Guides: In the final phase of the project, we will develop 6 policy briefs and 2 business guides based on the produced mitigation pathways (and potentially featuring technical briefs on the capabilities of the new models developed). These will consider underexplored interactions with extreme events, circular

economy, geopolitical tensions, lifestyle changes, and more. Each of the briefs will have their own newsletter and will be distributed to stakeholders; building on our partners' networks, experience, and success in interacting with policymakers, industry, and other stakeholders, these briefs and guides will be written in nontechnical language, using a distinctive visual identity template.

Newsletters: Conditional on available project content, 6-10 newsletters are expected to be sent during the remaining months of the project. Newsletter subscribers will be also increased by promoting the newsletter to our social media, partners' social media and other interested parties. The circulation of project newsletters and press releases will be intensified in the final year to boost the project's visibility, increase website traffic, encourage participation and promote attendance at DIAMOND events.

Infographics: Infographics & Videos: The project will prioritise the production of three infographics and two short videos highlighting key modelling outputs, use cases, and stakeholder engagement insights. These will be disseminated via social media and hosted on the project website.

Synergies with Ongoing Projects: Strengthen collaborations with IAMC, ECEMF, and EGU through joint events, and shared newsletters.

All CDE activities will culminate to the final event of DIAMOND which will be organised during the last month of the project. We are currently exploring two options for planning the final event. The first option includes following the setup and format of the final event of IAM COMPACT⁹⁰, which took place in August 2025 in the Acropolis Museum in Athens, Greece (see Figure 14 for the agenda and a photo of the event). To make the IAM COMPACT event attractive to the wider community of Greek researchers, policymakers, and civil society, the event also had a session on the net-zero transition of Greece and was a collaboration with ELLET, the Greek Society for Environment and Cultural Heritage in Greece. This strategy was successful as the event had 154 participants overall.

EPU
N T U A

ELLENIKI ENIMERIA
Hellenic Society for Environment and Cultural Heritage

IAM COMPACT

RESPONSIVE SCIENCE IN SUPPORT OF CLIMATE POLICYMAKING
Friday, August 29, 2025
Acropolis Museum, Athens, Greece

A G E N D A

09:30 – 10:00 Registrations, coffee, and get-together

10:00 – 10:30 **Introductory remarks**

- Introduction to the IAM COMPACT project (Alexandros Nikas, National Technical University of Athens)
- A policy response mechanism for policy-relevant modelling systems (Ugne Kalatauskaitė, Biogen)

10:30 – 11:45 **Delivering on the European Green Deal: EU-wide resilience, Member States, citizens, and justice**

- Security, flexibility, and resilience in the EU (Pavlos Magni Johansson, Aalborg University)
- Aligning NDCs with the T14 by 55' targets (Natalia Prilgova, National Technical University of Athens)
- Distributional impacts of EU climate policy (Jon Samundset, Bioscience Centre for Climate Change)
- Lifestyle changes towards net zero (Gonzalo Pinedo Hernandez, University of Valladolid)
- Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Yannis-Orestis Pappadimitrou (n.g.)

11:45 – 13:00 **Trade and industry: How can Europe remain competitive towards net zero?**

- EU steel industry: offshoring, retooling, and relocation (Alexander Jäger, Wuppertal Institut)
- Renewable hydrogen trade in a global decarbonised energy system (Zivkica Mihal, CICERO)
- Geopolitically constrained pathways to carbon neutrality (Ekaterina Zisoua, E3-Modelling S.A.)
- Understanding the trade-climate-industry nexus in a fragmenting world (Mark Baker, E3-Modelling S.A.)
- Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Christina Tigka (Inst. of Communication & Computer Systems)

13:00 – 14:00 Lunch break

14:00 – 15:00 **A deep dive into Greece's net zero transition**

- Climate change impacts in Greece (Christos Giannakopoulos, National Observatory of Athens)
- Greece's new NDCP & funding requirements (Dimitris Kollias, Hellenic Ministry of Environment and Energy)
- Towards a decarbonised built environment in Greece (Nikolaos Kivathis, University of Piraeus)
- Adaptation, resilience, environment, and national heritage (Vasiliki Pringkeke, ELLET)
- Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Thomas Doxidas (doxidas+, ELLET)

15:00 – 16:00 **Climate action and broader sustainable development: trade-offs and co-benefits**

- Cross-sectoral mitigation and SDGs (Konstantinos Koussis, National Technical University of Athens)
- Biodiversity, material resources, & biophysical limits (Theo Routledge, Bioscience Centre for Climate Change)
- Land-use policies and renewable energy expansion (Noelia Ferreras Alonso, CARTIF)
- The impact of disruptive events in climate planning (Klas Al Khouridze, Imperial College London)
- Panel discussion, including Q&A – Moderation by Dimitra Spalathidou (HOLISTIC S.A.)

16:00 – 16:10 Policy Intervention: Haris Doukas, Mayor of Athens

16:10 – 16:50 **Developing new technical capabilities in countries with limited domestic capacity**

- A novel framework for capacity development (Francesco Gardumi, KTH Royal Institute of Technology)
- New energy modelling capacity in Ukraine amidst conflict (Darya Dudarev, Kyiv School of Economics)
- Novel nexus modelling in recession-hit Sri Lanka (Lakshy Theodorou, Rajarata University of Sri Lanka)
- Whole-systems analysis and polyrisks: Ethiopia (Camilla Lo Gulicchio, KTH Royal Institute of Technology)
- Capacity building in Kenyan academia (Chandana Seneviratne, KTH Royal Institute of Technology)

16:50 – 17:00 Conclusions

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Figure 14. IAM COMPACT final event as a template for DIAMOND's final event

Second, we can organise the final event of DIAMOND in the context of the 2026 Annual Meeting of the Integrated

⁹⁰ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/iam-compact_climate-energygpolicy-greendeal-activity-7369692731662569472-0YEF

Assessment Modelling Consortium⁹¹. This option might be more fitting for DIAMOND as most of its key exploitable results are intended for the modelling community. Having a dedicated DIAMOND session in one of the biggest conferences for climate-economy modelling would provide ideal publicity and dissemination, as well as offer a chance to further foster the communities of practice of each model, ensuring that the impact of DIAMOND and its models extend beyond the duration of the project.

⁹¹ <https://www.iamconsortium.org>

7 References

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